

Kinetic Study of Hydrolysis of *N*-Salicylidene-*o*-methylaniline Spectrophotometrically[#]

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Kinetics of hydrolysis of the Schiff base, *N*-salicylidene-*o*-methylaniline (HL) have been studied in the pH range 3.57–12.65 in the temperature range 29–45°. A rate profile diagram of pH vs rate constant, shows a rate minimum in the pH range 6.30–12.00 and reaches a plateau at pH > 12.30. Suitable reaction mechanisms have been suggested for the hydrolyses of the Schiff base in acidic, neutral and basic media. From the effect of temperature on the rate, various thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated.

The study of the formation and hydrolysis of imines assumes importance due to its close relation to the conversion of C=O to C=N and vice versa in biochemical processes^{1,2}. Much work has been done on the complexation of metal ions with Schiff bases with a view to study the structure and stability of the resultant complexes. The catalytic effect of hydrogen, hydroxyl and metal ions on the formation and hydrolysis of Schiff bases has also been studied²⁻⁵. We report herein the kinetics and mechanism of hydrolysis of the Schiff base, *N*-salicylidene-*o*-methylaniline at different pH values.

Results and Discussion

The rate constant values in the pH range 3.57–12.65 at 29° are listed in Table 1. A rate profile diagram of pH vs rate constant at 29° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ shows the rate minimum at $7.04 < \text{pH} < 12.00$. The rate is almost constant at pH > 12.30 (Fig. 1)

Rate-limiting pathways : In the pH range 3.57–12.65, the Schiff base (HL) may be assumed to undergo hydrolysis by four rate-determining pathways⁵: (i) an acid-catalysed path involving the addition of water to the imine linkage of the protonated imine, H_2L^+ (k_1), (ii) a spontaneous path involving the addition of water to the imine linkage of the neutral imine, HL, (k_2), (iii) a

Fig 1 Plot of k against pH at 29° for the hydrolysis of *N*-salicylidene-*o*-methylaniline at $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

path involving the addition of water to the imine anion, L^- (k_3) and (iv) a path involving the addition of hydroxyl ion to the imine anion, L (k_4). The last step in which hydroxyl ion predominates may be eliminated as the rate constant was found to be almost independent of hydroxyl ion concentration at pH > 12.30 (Table 1). Thus the overall rate of hydrolysis will be

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 (\text{H}_2\text{L}^+) + k_2 (\text{HL}) + k_3 (\text{L}^-) \quad (1)$$

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TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT DATA FOR HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-SALICYLIDENE-*O*-METHYLANILINE

Ethanol-Water = 40% (v/v), Temp = 29°, μ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

pH	[H ⁺] × 10 ⁷ mol dm ⁻³	[OH ⁻] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k × 10 ³ s ⁻¹
3.57	2692.00	—	16.70
4.36	436.50	—	5.90
4.58	263.00	—	2.50
5.06	87.10	—	1.00
5.42	38.02	—	0.40
6.30	5.01	—	0.10
7.04	0.91	—	0.11
12.00	—	10.00	0.40
12.30	—	19.95	1.40
12.39	—	24.55	1.70
12.60	—	39.81	2.00
12.65	—	44.67	2.06

Hydrolysis of Schiff base in acidic and neutral range of pH : The rate constant varies linearly with hydrogen ion concentration in the pH range 4.36–7.04 (Table 1). In this pH range, equation (1) reduces to (2),

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 (\text{H}_2\text{L}^+) + k_2 (\text{HL})$$

$$k = \frac{k_1}{K_1} (\text{H}^+) + k_2 \quad (2)$$

A plot of *k* vs [H⁺] was found to be a straight line with slope *k*₁/*K*₁ from which *k*₁ was calculated to be 4.47 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ at 29°. Since the intercept of the plot is zero, *k*₂ is taken as zero. In the acidic pH range, the proton-catalysed attack of water on the reactive imine linkage of (HL) is suggested to be the rate-limiting

Scheme 1

step for the hydrolysis (Scheme 1). The extremely low rates in the neutral pH range are due to negligible protonation of (HL). Consequently, the attack of water on the protonated imine is very slow. The addition of water to the neutral imine⁶ is therefore suggested to be the rate-limiting step.

TABLE 2—GENERAL ACID-BASE CATALYSIS FOR HYDROLYSIS OF *N*-SALICYLIDENE-*O*-METHYLANILINE

Ethanol-Water 40% (v/v), Temp = 29°, μ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

Potassium hydrogen phthalate (PHP) and hydrochloric acid buffer (pH = 3.57)

[(PHP) + (HCl)] (× 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)	2.25	4.50	6.75	9.00	11.25
<i>k</i> (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	16.20	16.28	14.63	16.92	17.27

Acetate buffer (pH = 4.58)

[(HA) + (A ⁻)] (× 10 ² mol dm ⁻³)	8.00	16.00	24.00	32.00	40.00
<i>k</i> (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	2.19	2.04	1.96	2.6	2.20

Phosphate buffer (pH = 7.04)

(H ₂ PO ₄) + (HPO ₄ ²⁻) (× 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)	8.00	16.00	24.00	32.00	40.00
<i>k</i> (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.11	0.11

Carbonate buffer (pH = 10.76)

[(HCO ₃ ⁻) + (CO ₃ ²⁻)] (× 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)	4.00	8.00	12.00	16.00	20.00
<i>k</i> (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)					

In the hydrolysis study specific acid catalysis is assumed as no general catalysis was observed (Table 2).

Hydrolysis of Schiff base in basic medium :
 In the basic range, $\text{pH} > 11.75$, the rate constant initially increases with increase in pH and is nearly independent of hydroxyl ion concentration at $\text{pH} > 12.30$ (Table 1). In this pH range, the Schiff base may be assumed to be exclusively in the anionic form L^- ($\text{p}K_2 = 9.709$) due to the neutralisation of the phenolic proton of the *ortho*-hydroxy group by the OH^- ion of alkali⁵. The above observations lead to the assumption that the complex formed may be 'Arrhenius complex'. In the presence of excess catalyst, 'Arrhenius complex' leads to 'specific hydroxyl ion catalysis' at low hydroxyl ion concentration and the rate reaches a limiting value at high hydroxyl ion concentration⁶. In the present study, the rate increases with the hydroxyl ion concentration at low hydroxyl ion concentrations. Since no general catalysis was observed in this region (Table 2), specific hydroxyl ion catalysis may be assumed. Further, the rate reaches a limiting value at higher

hydroxyl ion concentrations. All these facts indicate that the rate-limiting step is the slow reaction of the Schiff base anion L^- with water (k_4)^{5,7} (Scheme 2). The average value of the rate constants at $\text{pH} > 12.30$ is taken as $k_4 = 1.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 29° .

Effect of temperature and activation parameters :
 The hydrolysis of the Schiff base was carried out at four temperatures : 29, 35, 40 and 45° . From the effect of temperature on the reaction rate, the various activation parameters, like energy of activation (E), $\Delta H^\ddagger$, $\Delta G^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ were evaluated. Activation entropy values in the acidic pH range are negative and practically constant till the neutral pH . This is because the protonated water molecule is held up at the nitrogen atom of the imine linkage. The adjacent bulky methyl group will not much hinder the free orientation of the water molecules and consequently there is a decrease in entropy, i.e. $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is negative ranging from -107.57 to $-264.30 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The negative activation entropies can perhaps be explained by a model in which water molecules are tightly held to the imine linkage, the nucleus of the hydrolytic reaction. The large negative values observed may indicate an extensive re-orientation of solvent molecules as a result of the formation of the activated complex³.

In the alkaline region, the water molecule alone will be much closer to the nitrogen atom of the imine linkage and the methyl group may greatly hinder the free orientation of the water molecules resulting in the increase of entropy, i.e. $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is positive, ranging from 25.36 to $178.66 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Experimental

The Schiff base was prepared by refluxing calculated amounts of salicylaldehyde and *o*-toluidine in ethanolic medium for about 1 h. On cooling, yellow coloured crystals of the Schiff base that appeared were crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 40° . The structure was confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra.

Kinetic measurements : The hydrolysis of the Schiff base was studied spectrophotometrically in

Scheme 2

a series of universal buffer solutions in the pH range 3.57–12.65 in 40% ethanol-water medium. The pH values of these buffers were determined using an Elico LI-120 pH meter. The temperature was varied between 29 and 45° over the above pH range. The concentration of the Schiff base was kept at 4×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³. The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was maintained at $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ by using 1 M sodium perchlorate (E. Merck). All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck).

In a typical kinetic run, a solution of sodium perchlorate, buffer and absolute ethanol in requisite amounts was allowed to equilibrate in a previously adjusted thermostat. The reaction was initiated by adding a known volume of the stock solution of the Schiff base in ethanol which was also maintained at the same temperature. After mixing, the reaction mixture was immediately transferred to a quartz cell and the decrease of absorbance of the Schiff base with time was followed against the reagent blank kept in another quartz cell. The decrease of absorbance with time was followed at $\lambda = 390$ nm, using an Elico CL-54 spectrophotometer. The first absorbance reading could be recorded 25 s after the mixing of the constituents of the reaction mixture.

The plots of $\log (A_t - A_\infty)$ against time were found to be straight-lines and the pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the slopes. From the effect of temperature on the reaction rate, the energy of activation (E) and other activation parameters were evaluated.

Equilibrium constants : The deprotonation and protonation of the Schiff base (HL) may be represented as

pK_1 was determined by a potentiometric titration of 4×10^{-4} M Schiff base against 0.01 M HCl using a pH meter equipped with a combined glass-calomel electrode assembly. pK_1 was found to be 4.357 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 29° and $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³.

The Schiff base anion (L^-) showed an absorption maximum at 390 nm. pK_2 was calculated spectrophotometrically⁵ as 9.709 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 29° and $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³.

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